

This document exemplifies the framework’s application to an illustrative scenario of an SoS in operation at a large Brazilian public university.

Scenario description

The SoS was implemented to support responding to electrical power supply interruption incidents. The fast response to these incidents is especially important for two facilities of the institution: i) the data center that hosts information systems that support all administrative and academic activities of the institution, in addition to hosting critical systems for the functioning of a university hospital; and ii) animal research center, which adopts rigorous ventilation and air conditioning parameters to make research viable. The constituent systems of this SoS are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Software systems of the SoS in operation in the university.

Constituent system	Description
Power Generator Management System (PGMS)	A system maintained and operated by the campus electrical department. It identifies local power outages and provides information on the fuel level in the generators.
General Power System (GPS)	A system maintained and operated by the campus electrical department. It reports the status of the electricity supply at the main campus substation.
UPS Management System (UPSMS)	A System maintained and operated by the campus electrical department. It provides information about the electrical energy consumption and the UPS batteries’ level of autonomy.
Telephony Gateway (TG)	A system maintained and operated by the IT department. It notifies the person in charge of an interruption in the power supply via a telephone call.

Furthermore, a system was developed to mediate communication between constituent systems. We call this system the Orchestrator. This SoS operates as follows:

1. The Orchestrator monitors the status of the local electricity supply through queries to the PGMS;
2. If an interruption is detected, the Orchestrator waits 300 seconds and makes a new query. Sometimes the supply is interrupted for a few seconds, and this 300-second wait prevents the person in charge from being called unnecessarily on weekends or at dawn;
3. If the power supply is still interrupted, the Orchestrator queries the fuel level in the PGMS. In addition, consult the UPSMS for information on current consumption and UPS autonomy (determined by battery charge);
4. The Orchestrator calculates the total autonomy, considering the current consumption of electricity, the fuel level of the generators, and the autonomy level of the UPS batteries;
5. The Orchestrator consults the GPS to verify whether the interruption is local or campus-wide;

6. The Telephony Gateway sends a voice recording to the on-call phone informing about the interruption in the energy supply and informing the total autonomy time.

The constituent systems are independent and serve specific purposes. Also, the implementation of the SoS was an initiative of the IT department, which requested access to the systems maintained by the electrical engineering department. However, the electrical engineering department is not engaged in the operation of the SoS. This causes problems that compromise the response to the interruption in the electricity supply on the campus. The main problems are:

- **#P1 - Telephony Gateway unavailability:** the Telephony Gateway is installed in a location far from the data center and it lacks the appropriate infrastructure. The network switch that provides connectivity to the telephony gateway is connected to old UPS without much autonomy. Sometimes, in the event of an interruption in the power supply, the UPS shuts down within a few seconds, causing the network equipment to shut down. When this occurs, the orchestrator cannot activate the Telephony Gateway to make the phone call;
- **#P2 - GPS unavailability:** This software system experiences the same problem as the Telephony Gateway. When it becomes unavailable, it is not possible to verify whether the outage is local or campus-wide;
- **#P3 - Fuel Level Sensor Unavailability:** The fuel sensor stops working for unknown reasons. When this occurs, it is not possible to calculate the total autonomy. It is necessary to manually reset the sensor for it to return to operation.

Framework application

This section describes the framework's application on the SoS described in the previous section. We focus mainly on the activities of the Preparation cycle, as this cycle comprises activities carried out by professionals. The application of the activities of the SoS Characterization phase is described in the following.

Mission decomposition: We use mKAOS for mission decomposition. mKAOS is a specific notation for mission specification in SoS. In the mission decomposition, we identify the responsibility of each of the constituent systems. The decomposition diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Definition of capabilities requirements: Next, we define the capability requirements, i.e., how SoS capabilities should be delivered to fulfill the missions identified in the previous activity. For example, it may consider time constraints, performance, and security. Table 2 describes SoS capabilities requirements.

Identification of the states of interest of the constituent systems: We define the states of interest of the constituent systems for each capability requirement identified earlier. The state of interest is the state in which a constituent system is able to meet capacity requirements. For the sake of simplicity,

Figure 1: Mission decomposition.

Table 2: Capabilities requirements.

ID	Capability requirement
REQ01	SoS SHALL notify the electrical engineering team immediately after 300 seconds of power interruption.
REQ02	SoS SHALL notify if the outage is local or campus-wide.
REQ03	SoS SHALL notify the team via phone call.
REQ04	SoS SHALL calculate the total autonomy so the team can plan the actions.

we assume that the fact that the constituent systems are available is sufficient for fulfilling the capabilities requirements defined in the previous activity. Table 3 lists the states of interest associated with capabilities requirements.

Identification of observation points of the constituent systems: The definition observation points is the last activity of the SoS characterization phase. We defined the “Ping” (ICMP request and ICMP reply messages) to check the availability of the constituent systems. “Ping” is typically used to verify if the target computer in a network is available.

The following activities are part of the definition of the transient architectural configurations phase.

Specification of mission requirements for the transient architectural configurations: In this activity, non-critical capacity requirements are relaxed to prioritize critical ones. The main idea is that these requirements are considered in the subsequent activity, in which the transient architectural configurations are defined. Table 4 describes the requirements defined in this

Table 3: States of interest.

Capability requirement	State of interest
REQ01	- TG available
REQ02	- GPS available
REQ03	- TG available
REQ04	- PGMS fuel sensors available - UPSMS available

activity. We use operators from RELAX [1], a language to support the requirements engineering for self-adaptive systems.

Table 4: Capabilities requirements for the transient architectural configurations.

ID	Capability requirement
REQ01'	SoS SHALL notify the electrical engineering team immediately after 300 seconds of power interruption (invariant).
REQ02'	EVENTUALLY , SoS SHALL notify if the outage is local or campus-wide.
REQ03'	EVENTUALLY , SoS SHALL notify the team via phone call.
REQ04'	EVENTUALLY , SoS SHALL calculate the total autonomy so the team can plan the actions.

Transient architectural configurations description: This activity must consider the requirements defined in the previous step. In addition, each transient configuration must be associated with one or more violations of states of interest. For illustrative purposes, we have defined a transient architectural configuration for each problem described in the scenario description. We omit architectural details, such as the definition of communication interfaces, and focus only on SoS composition.

For the Telephony Gateway unavailability issue, we defined an architectural configuration that replaces it with an email service. This does not require replacing other constituent systems and requires the Orchestrator to be able to send messages through the email service. The composition of this transient architectural configuration would be an e-mail service, GPS, PGMS, and UPSMS.

The unavailability of GPS implies that it is impossible to verify whether the interruption in the electrical supply is campus-wide or just local. Therefore, we chose to omit this information from the notification, as this information is not critical as the electrical engineering team can diagnose this issue when on the location. The transient architectural configuration would consist of Telephony Gateway, PGMS, and UPSMS.

Finally, for the problem of the unavailability of the fuel level sensors, we chose to do the range calculation without considering the fuel level. That is, the autonomy calculation would only consider the current consumption and the autonomy time of the UPS batteries. Furthermore, it is important to mention that the PGMS maintains regular operation even in the unavailability of the sensors. This means detecting an interruption in the electrical energy supply is still possible. Therefore, the transient architectural configuration composition

would be the Telephony Gateway, PGMS, UPSMS, and GPS.

After the Preparation cycle, a monitoring agent must collect data from the previously defined constituent systems' observation points. In this illustrative example, a monitoring agent should check the availability of the Telephony Gateway, PGMS, GPS, UPSMS, and fuel level sensors. Furthermore, suppose one of the constituent systems is not operating in the defined state of interest. Then, the monitoring agent must inform the Orchestrator that a reconfiguration must occur.

References

- [1] J. Whittle, P. Sawyer, N. Bencomo, B. H. C. Cheng, J.-M. Bruel, Relax: A language to address uncertainty in self-adaptive systems requirement, *Requirements Engineering* 15 (2) (2010) 177–196.